

Establishing priority quality traits thresholds through correlation between instrumental measurements and sensory panel data

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Gérard NGOH NEWILAH, University of Dschang, Dschang, Cameroon

Cédric KENDINE VEPOWO, University of Douala, Douala, Cameroon

Socrate GOUMMELI, University of Dschang, Dschang, Cameroon

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This document has been contributed to/reviewed by:

Oluwatoyin AYETIGBO (CIRAD)
Zoe DEUSCHER (CIRAD)

08/03/2025
13/03/2025

Final validation by:

Eglantine FAUVELLE (CIRAD)

25/03/2025

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ABSTRACT

Inadequate attention to postharvest quality in conventional plantain breeding pipelines limits their effectiveness. Understanding the key quality traits of boiled plantain that consumers prefer could be of great interest for the adoption of new selected clones. This report aimed to establish priority quality traits thresholds through correlation between instrumental and sensory attributes of boiled plantain genotypes. Consumer tests, including Just About Right and Check All That Apply, as well as sensory quantitative descriptive analysis (QDA), instrumental texture profile analysis (TPA), and penetrometry, were conducted with nine accessions: three landraces and six plantain-like bred hybrids. More than 45% of participants rated landraces as just-about-right for all sensory attributes (humidity, sweetness, color, and firmness), characterized by appealing traits such as smooth appearance, attractiveness, mealiness, firmness, distinct plantain taste, and yellow color. Color and firmness received the highest scores from panelists for landraces. Penetrometry was more effective in discriminating genotypes than TPA. For TPA, the most discriminatory attributes were hardness, gumminess, resilience and chewiness, while hardness was key for penetrometry. No correlation existed between penetrometry and sensory texture, but TPA revealed negative correlations between sensory humidity and hardness, as well as between sensory firmness and resilience, with a positive correlation between resilience and sensory humidity. Threshold values for some priority quality traits are: Wetness=32.03%; Firmness=8737.31g and Sweetness=13.90°Brix. Regarding color, no threshold value was found with the available data. Combining QDA with instrumental measurements could enhance the selection process for plantain hybrids and facilitate the adoption of new varieties.

Keywords: Consumer testing, Texture Profile Analysis, Penetrometry, Efficient breeding, clone adoption

1 INTRODUCTION

Plantain, an important staple food in tropical and subtropical regions of Africa, Asia and Central and South America, presents difficulties in identifying cultivars based on morphological characteristics alone (Shaibu *et al.*, 2003). In West and Central Africa, plantain is often cooked in a variety of ways, eaten green or ripe, with boiled plantain being particularly popular in Cameroon (Nghoh Newilah *et al.*, 2005 ; Nghoh Newilah *et al.*, 2018). Varietal improvement has focused mainly on agronomic performance and disease resistance, often neglecting consumer preferences (Eriksson *et al.*, 2018). As a result, very few plantain-like hybrids have been widely adopted. Given the growing demand, it is essential to develop new clones that meet the needs of end-users. Product quality assessment involves a variety of methods, including color scales for visual appearance (Pathare *et al.*, 2013), sound assessment using trained panels or acoustic techniques (Deliza *et al.*, 1996), flavour profiles using structured questionnaires (Lawless *et al.*, 2010), mouthfeel assessment using trained sensory panels (Stone *et al.*, 2012) and texture analysis using instrumental methods such as Texture Profile Analysis (TPA). (Bourne *et al.*, 2002)

Although sensory analysis provides detailed information on sensory properties, helps optimize product formulation and identifies key drivers of consumer preferences, it is time-consuming and subject to expert bias (Lawless *et al.*, 2010 ; Stone *et al.*, 2012 ; Ennis and Rousseau, 2017). Texture analysis provides objective and quantitative data, but may not always match consumer preferences or take into account other sensory attributes (Bourne *et al.*, 2002; Szczesniak, 2002).

To better assess the quality of boiled plantain, we need to identify its key attributes and correlate the sensory profile with instrumental measurements to improve the accuracy and speed of assessment (Malone *et al.*, 2003). TPA, an objective method for analysing texture characteristics, plays a crucial role in developing products that meet consumer expectations (Szczesniak, 1963). Recent studies have highlighted the preferred quality characteristics of plantain cultivars to improve the adoption of new plantain clones (Marimo *et al.*, 2020 ; Nghoh Newilah *et al.*, 2021). The development of a complete profile of boiled plantain requires the integration of consumer preferences, as well as sensory and instrumental texture analysis, to establish correlations between these parameters and thus accelerate the acceptance of new hybrids.

Quantitative descriptive analysis (QDA) is recognized as a tool for measuring the sensory attributes of food products, serving as a basis for the development of sensory profiles (Stone and Sidel, 1998). Therefore, the objective of this report was to establish priority quality traits thresholds through correlation between instrumental and sensory texture attributes of boiled plantain genotypes collected in Cameroon.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Plant material

Plantain bunches were collected from some accessions at their optimal physiological maturity from various experimental plots in Cameroon. These locations included the IITA plots in Mbal Mayo (approximately 640 m elevation), CARBAP plots in Bansa (around 1300 m elevation), and Njombe (about 80 m elevation). The accessions comprised three local landraces—*Batard*, *Big Ebanga*, and *Kelong Mekintu*—as well as four hybrids developed by IITA (PITA 14, PITA 21, PITA 23, and PITA 27) and two hybrids from CARBAP (*CARBAP 969* and *CARBAP K74*). Images and key characteristics of these accessions are presented in Figure 1 and Table 1. However, due to insufficient quantities of plantain bunches, the IITA-bred hybrids were not available for consumer testing.

2.2 Sample preparation

Plantain fruits from the second and third hands were selected, washed, peeled, weighed and soaked in water to prevent oxidative browning. The quantity of water was based on pulp:water ratio of 1:4. This water was

brought to boil in an aluminum pot (30cm wide, 16cm high and 0.4cm thick) using butane as the heat source. The pulps were introduced once the water started boiling (95°C \pm T°C \pm 100°C), and their boiling times were determined following previous laboratory works (Fangueng, 2022). For bred hybrids, boiling was completed after 45 minutes, when the pulp is sufficiently cooked, while landraces were cooked for 60 minutes. After boiling, plantain pulps were drained and kept in a thermos flask containing hot water (temperature \geq 95°C) in order to maintain samples at temperature between 55-60°C during sensory evaluation. Plantain clones were cooked in triplicate.

2.3 Consumer testing

In Cameroon, a study involving 123 untrained consumers evaluated two landraces of plantain (*Batard* and *Big Ebanga*) and two bred hybrids (*CARBAP K74* and *CARBAP 969*). The plantain fruits were sliced into 2 cm cylindrical pieces, placed on disposable plates, and presented to participants individually. After tasting each sample, consumers rinsed their mouths with mineral water before trying the next sample. The slices were kept at a temperature between 50 and 60°C, monitored with a kitchen thermometer.

Participants completed a questionnaire that collected personal information such as gender, country of residence, ethnic group, education, marital status, and their consumption habits regarding boiled plantain (including frequency and accompanying ingredients). The testing methods employed included a hedonic test, a Just About Right (JAR) test, and a Check All That Apply (CATA) test (Fliedel and Bechoff, 2018).

Table 1. Average fruit characteristics of raw plantain accessions evaluated in this study.

Accessions	Cultivar type	Fruit weight (g)	Pulp weight (g)	Peel weight (g)	Pu/pe* ratio	Fruit grade (cm)	Fruit length (cm)
<i>CARBAP 969</i>	Bred hybrid	212.6 (4.4)	125.8 (1.8)	85.0 (5.3)	1.5 (0.1)	4.0 (0.1)	21.3 (1.5)
<i>CARBAP K74</i>	Bred hybrid	216.9 (18.0)	135.8 (13.3)	80.2 (5.1)	1.7 (0.1)	3.8 (0.1)	22.0 (1.0)
<i>PITA 14</i>	Bred hybrid	115.4 (10.0)	70.4 (3.8)	44.0 (7.6)	1.6 (0.1)	3.3 (0.1)	19.0 (1.0)
<i>PITA 21</i>	Bred hybrid	121.7 (12.7)	65.7 (4.2)	55.2 (8.8)	1.2 (0.1)	3.6 (0.1)	20.7 (1.5)
<i>PITA 23</i>	Bred hybrid	105.5 (6.7)	57.1 (3.9)	51.1 (1.4)	1.1 (0.1)	3.3 (0.1)	17.0 (1.0)
<i>PITA 27</i>	Bred hybrid	119.6 (6.01)	74.6 (3.3)	44.7 (4.0)	1.7 (0.1)	3.2 (0.2)	17.3 (0.6)
<i>Batard</i>	Landrace	281.9 (73.9)	173.3 (50.7)	107.2 (22.8)	1.6 (0.1)	4.3 (0.2)	25.3 (2.5)
<i>Big Ebanga</i>	Landrace	215.3 (8.1)	131.1 (4.3)	83.4 (4.0)	1.6 (0.0)	3.8 (0.2)	23.3 (0.6)
<i>Kelong mekintu</i>	Landrace	168.4 (6.6)	108.8 (3.1)	58.9 (3.8)	1.9 (0.1)	3.3 (0.1)	18.7 (1.2)

*Pu/Pe : Pulp to peel ratio

Standard deviations are in brackets

Table 2. Physicochemical and color characteristics of raw plantain per accession prior to QDA

GENOTYPES	Pulp firmness (kgf)	TTA (meq/100g)	TSS ($^{\circ}$ Brix)	DMC (%)	L*	a*	b*
<i>CARBAP 969</i>	2.27	177.78	0.80	32.02	78.31	1.84	37.35
<i>CARBAP K74</i>	3.32	216.67	0.60	29.68	81.10	0.10	38.90
<i>Batard</i>	3.19	205.56	1.15	39.56	79.22	5.20	38.42
<i>PITA 14</i>	2.25	222.22	1.00	32.51	74.16	4.09	34.13
<i>PITA 21</i>	3.01	166.67	0.35	31.75	83.81	0.18	32.41
<i>PITA 23</i>	1.81	300.00 ^c	1.60	29.38	78.39	2.59	37.39
<i>PITA 27</i>	2.66	200.00	0.80	33.30	81.86	0.92	32.06
<i>Big Ebanga</i>	3.21	183.28	1.00	38.07	78.95	4.37	37.44
<i>Kelong mekintu</i>	3.23	161.11	0.80	36.58	78.67	3.53	36.46

TTA: Total Titratable Acidity; TSS: Total Soluble Solids; DMC: Dry Matter Content

Colour values are described by L*=lightness, a*=redness, b*=yellowness on the CIE LAB Colour Chart (CIE=International Commission on Illumination)

Photo 1. A bunch of *CARBAP 969*

Photo 2. A bunch of *CARBAP K74*

Photo 3. A bunch of *PITA14*

Photo 4. A bunch of *PITA21*

Photo 5. A bunch of *PITA23*

Photo 6. A bunch of *PITA27*

Photo 7. A bunch of *Batard*

Photo 8. A bunch of *Big Ebanga*

Photo 9. A bunch of *Kelong Mekintu*

Figure 1. Some plantain clones used within the framework of this study

2.4 Plant material

Quantitative Descriptive Analysis (QDA) was used to assess the sensory attributes of nine different plantain genotypes. A panel consisting of ten trained assessors, including three women and seven men, conducted the evaluations. The assessment followed protocols established by Maraval *et al.* (2018).

- For the pre-selection and recruitment of panelists, individuals were recruited voluntarily through a simple application process or internally following a call from the Postharvest Technology laboratory. Generally, if the panel is to consist of X subjects, it is advisable to recruit and train at least 1.5X individuals. Care was taken during recruitment to ensure a balanced representation of men and women, as well as a good age distribution among potential panelists (ranging from 18 to 60 years).
- Regarding the training and selection of panelists, they were trained to identify and describe sensory attributes using standardized vocabulary (ISO, 2009). Training sessions utilized reference samples with known sensory properties. The main sensory tests performed for training and selection included a basic flavor and sensation recognition test, a basic flavors classification test, and a threshold test for the perception of basic flavors and sensations.
- For the calibration of panelists, selected individuals followed calibration process to ensure consistency in their sensory evaluations through five sessions, which involve generating vocabulary, creating a tasting form, using a scale, individual notation on a scale, and assessing panel performance.
- When conducting descriptive tests, evaluations were performed to assess the sensory properties of food products, using a structured evaluation form that includes a list of sensory attributes and a rating scale for each attribute. Panelists rate the intensity of each sensory attribute using this scale.

For data processing, the data collected from descriptive tests were analyzed to identify the sensory properties that differentiate the products. Statistical analyses were conducted using XLSTAT for Variance Analysis and Principal Component Analysis (PCA). Panel performance were monitored using the methodology described by Bugaud *et al.* (2022).

- **Data Input and Organization:** In an Excel spreadsheet, data concerning the samples (name, code), panelists (name, code, score), and tasting sessions (repetition and session numbers) were recorded. This information was organized first by session numbers and then by sample codes.
- **Panel Repeatability Assessment:** This assessment involved several steps, with panelist repeatability optimized under four conditions:
 - the absolute difference between two observations must be 3 or less on a scale of 0 to 10;
 - if a panelist was not repeatable for an attribute during a session, their scores for that attribute were excluded for all products in that session;
 - a panelist was considered repeatable for an attribute if they maintained repeatability in over 50% of all sessions; and
 - a panelist who was not repeatable for more than 50% of the attributes was eliminated.
- **Panelists' Agreement Evaluation and Data Cleaning:** The agreement among panelists was optimized under three conditions:
 - agreement was deemed effective if the absolute difference in scores for a given product between the panel's average and each panelist's score was 3 or less on a scale of 0 to 10;
 - if more than 50% of a panelist's data for an attribute were not align with the panel's scores, that data were discarded; and
 - a panelist who disagrees with the panel on more than 50% of the attributes was removed.
- **Final Table Preparation:** A final mean table was created, displaying the average values obtained by the panel for each product and attribute on a 0 to 10 scale. This table was utilized for graphical (radar) and statistical analyses (PCA, linear regressions).

The characteristics of boiled plantains studied included sweetness, firmness, moisture, yellow color, and overall acceptability (see Table 3). These traits were evaluated using a rating scale from 0 to 10 (where 0 was the lowest score and 10 was the highest). The same tasting protocol (described in section 2.3) used for consumer testing was applied for the QDA

2.5 Texture analysis

The instrumental texture parameters of boiled plantain pulps were assessed through penetration (penetrometry) and double compression (TPA) using a Texture Analyzer (TA-XTplusC; Stable Microsystems Ltd, Godalming, UK). The protocol was developed by Ngoh Newilah & Kendine Vepowo (2022). For these analyses, fully cooked plantain pulps were drained and stored in a thermos box. A piece of boiled pulp was taken out, placed on a tray, and cut in half with a double-blade knife. All texture measurements were conducted at temperatures between 55 and 60°C, as measured with a digital thermometer. In the penetrometry test, a 40° conical Perspex probe penetrated the boiled plantain slice (2 cm long, with the dorsal side facing the probe) at a constant speed of 1 mm/s to a depth of 10 mm, and the maximum force applied during the measurement was recorded. For TPA, the cut plantain pulps were extruded using a hollow cylindrical rod (width: 2.9 cm; height: 2 cm) and placed on the texture analyzer plate. Two compression cycles, each corresponding to a 30% strain, were performed at a constant speed of 1 mm/s using a 35 mm diameter cylinder probe. The textural attributes measured included hardness, cohesiveness, adhesiveness, springiness, gumminess, and chewiness. TPA measurements were conducted on all clones, while penetrometry could not be performed for *CARBAP 969* due to a shortage of samples. Each sample underwent two cooking replicates, with at least eight readings taken per replicate.

2.6 Physicochemical and colour analysis

Total soluble solids (TSS) were measured using a handheld refractometer. Total titratable acidity (TTA) was determined manually through titration with 0.1 N sodium hydroxide until the endpoint was reached, indicated by a color change of the phenolphthalein from colorless to pink/red. The dry matter content (DMC) of cooked plantain pulps was determined by drying fresh samples in an oven at 105 °C until a constant weight was achieved. These procedures as well as color measurements using a chromameter, conducted in triplicate, were documented by Dadzie and Orchard (1997).

2.7 Statistical analyses

A one-way analysis of variance was conducted to identify significant differences in overall liking and attribute scores between the boiled plantain samples evaluated by consumers and panelists. Hierarchical cluster analysis (Ward's method) was used to group consumers based on similar acceptance levels. Tukey's test, with a 95% confidence interval, facilitated multiple pairwise comparisons. For each boiled plantain sample, the number of consumers rating specific characteristics as just-about-right, too weak, or too strong was counted, and the corresponding percentages were calculated. Principal component analysis (PCA) analyzed the relationship between the frequency of sensory characteristics cited in CATA and the mean overall liking scores for each sample. Statistical analyses for physicochemical data, consumer testing, and QDA data were performed using XLSTAT 2014. Texture analysis was conducted with Exponent Connect Software (version 8.0.9.0), while JMP (version 16) was used for texture-related data analysis. Pearson correlation coefficients at a 5% threshold were calculated, and linear regressions were applied to predict physicochemical and textural properties based on QDA parameters, focusing on those with at least 50% just-about-right ratings to determine acceptable threshold values.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Socio-demographic characteristics of respondents

The consumer study revealed that the number of participants from each locality was nearly equal, with 48.8% from Njombe and 51.2% from Mbanga. Men comprised 57.7% of the respondents. The predominant tribe was Bamileke (60.7%), followed by North Westerners (10.7%). Most participants were married (60.2%), and a large portion had completed secondary education, working as artisans, employees, or traders (22%). Boiled plantain was frequently consumed, with 31.7% of respondents eating it several times a week, typically paired with vegetables (61.8%) or sauce (51.2%), especially in the evening (73.2%) (Table 4).

3.2 Consumer testing and organoleptic characteristics of boiled plantain

The evaluation by 123 untrained consumers revealed significant differences in overall liking of the boiled plantain samples at $P < 0.05$. The *Batard* (6.9/10) and *Big Ebanga* (6.6/10) samples were the most favored, while *CARBAP 969* was only slightly liked, and *CARBAP K74* received a neutral score of 5.3/10 (Table 5).

Agglomerative hierarchical clustering identified three consumer groups: those who liked all samples, those who disliked *CARBAP 969* and *CARBAP K74*, and those who specifically disliked *CARBAP K74* (Figure 2). Moreover, consumers of the second group are more demanding than in other groups for all plantains, as the appreciation scores are lower than for the other groups. Responses regarding color, firmness, humidity, and sweetness of the boiled plantain samples, assessed on a Just-About-Right (JAR) scale, are detailed in Figure 3. Most consumers expressed satisfaction with the sensory attributes of *Batard* and *Big Ebanga*, although only 48.8% liked the sweetness of *Big Ebanga*. *CARBAP 969* showed acceptable humidity levels (53.7% JAR) but fell short in sweetness and firmness (44.7% JAR), and was notably deficient in color. Over 60% of respondents disliked *CARBAP K74* across all four characteristics.

Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was utilized to summarize the relationships among CATA sensory characteristics, the boiled plantain samples, and the mean overall liking scores. The PCA explained 96.5% of the variance in sensory characteristics, with the first two axes accounting for 82.9% and 13.6%, respectively. The first axis was primarily influenced positively by attributes like smoothness, attractiveness, mealiness, firmness, good aroma, plantain taste, yellow color, hardness, and dryness, associated with the more liked samples (*Batard* and *Big Ebanga*). In contrast, negative associations were linked to descriptors like sap taste, pale color, moisture, softness, and lack of odor, which were related to the least liked sample (*CARBAP K74*) (Figure 4).

Figure 2. Clustering of the consumers based on their overall liking (A) and mean overall liking of the boiled plantain samples by consumer clusters (B)

Table 3. Distribution of consumers surveyed according to demographic differences and consumer attitudes to boiled plantain.

Demographic criteria and consumer attitudes	Categories	Percent by criteria (123 consumers)
Locality	Njombe	48.8
	Mbanga	51.2
Gender	Female	42.3
	Male	57.7
Age (years)	18-25	9.8
	26-35	35.8
	36-45	21.1
	46-55	20.3
	≥56	13.0
Ethnicity	Bamileke	60.7
	Northwesterner	10.7
	Ewondo	3.3
	Balong	4.9
	Mbo'o	2.5
	Duala	7.4
	Northerner	2.5
	Yabassi	4.1
Others	4.1	
Education	No education	3.3
	Primary education	24.4
	Secondary education	56.9
	Higher education	15.4
Marital status	Single	34.1
	Married	60.2
	Widower	5.7
Occupation	Student	3.3
	Artisanship	28.5
	Civil servant	4.1
	Trading business	22.0
	Employee	26.8
	Unemployed	9.8
	Retired	2.4
	No response	3.3
Consumption frequency	Daily	5.7
	Several times a week	31.7
	One time a week	28.5
	Several times a month	26.0
	One time a month	2.4
	Rarely	5.7
Main consumption form*	With a sauce	51.2
	With vegetables	61.8
	With legumes	34.1
	With meat or roasted fish	20.3
	Others	5.7
Period of consumption*	Morning (breakfast)	28.5
	Noon (lunch)	57.7
	Evening (dinner)	73.2
	Between meals	6.5

*One or more responses were given

Table 4. Mean overall liking scores for boiled plantain samples tested

Boiled plantain samples	Mean Overall liking scores*	Groups**
<i>Batard</i>	6.9	A
<i>Big Ebanga</i>	6.6	A B
<i>CARBAP 969</i>	6.3	B
<i>CARBAP K74</i>	5.3	C

*Overall liking was rated on a nine-point scale from 1 = dislike extremely, to 9 = like extremely.

**Different letters correspond to the products, which are significantly different. Tukey test ($p < 0.05$).

Figure 3. Percentage of consumers who scored the four specific quality characteristics

Figure 4. Mapping of the sensory characteristics and the overall liking of the boiled plantain samples

3.3 Physicochemical composition, sensory and texture characteristics of boiled

3.3.1 Physicochemical composition of boiled plantain

The physicochemical analysis of boiled plantain samples showed significant differences ($P < 0.05$) across all parameters examined. *Batard* had the highest total titratable acidity (TTA), followed by *PITA 27*. Most bred hybrids, except for *PITA 23*, had significantly higher values compared to the landraces *Big Ebanga* and *Kelong Mekintu*. Similarly, *Batard* also recorded the highest total soluble solids (TSS), followed by *Big Ebanga* and *CARBAP K74*, both exceeding 10.0°Brix , while *PITA 23* had the lowest TSS. Additionally, dry matter content (DMC) was significantly higher in landraces, with *Batard* showing the highest value, whereas *PITA 21* and *PITA 27* had significantly lower DMC values.

Table 5. Physicochemical characteristics of boiled plantain per accession prior to Quantitative Descriptive Analysis

Accessions	TTA (mEq/100g)	TSS ($^{\circ}\text{Brix}$)	DMC (%)
<i>CARBAP 969</i>	$511.1 \pm 38.5^{\text{bcd}}$	$10.0 \pm 1.2^{\text{bcd}}$	$30.4 \pm 2.5^{\text{abc}}$
<i>CARBAP K74</i>	$511.1 \pm 38.5^{\text{bcd}}$	$12.6 \pm 0.7^{\text{bc}}$	$30.6 \pm 4.2^{\text{abc}}$
<i>PITA 14</i>	$577.8 \pm 38.5^{\text{abc}}$	$6.8 \pm 0.9^{\text{de}}$	$30.1 \pm 3.2^{\text{abc}}$
<i>PITA 21</i>	$577.8 \pm 38.5^{\text{abc}}$	$4.6 \pm 0.6^{\text{ef}}$	$26.5 \pm 0.7^{\text{c}}$
<i>PITA 23</i>	$422.2 \pm 38.5^{\text{d}}$	$2.4 \pm 0.4^{\text{f}}$	$31.1 \pm 1.0^{\text{abc}}$
<i>PITA 27</i>	$622.2 \pm 77.0^{\text{ab}}$	$12.0 \pm 0.9^{\text{bc}}$	$26.9 \pm 1.8^{\text{bc}}$
<i>Batard</i>	$666.7 \pm 66.7^{\text{a}}$	$16.4 \pm 2.8^{\text{a}}$	$33.7 \pm 1.8^{\text{a}}$
<i>Big Ebanga</i>	$444.4 \pm 38.5^{\text{cd}}$	$13.0 \pm 1.6^{\text{ab}}$	$32.9 \pm 1.5^{\text{ab}}$
<i>Kelong Mekintu</i>	$422.2 \pm 38.5^{\text{d}}$	$9.2 \pm 0.4^{\text{cd}}$	$33.4 \pm 0.3^{\text{a}}$
AVERAGE	528.4 ± 45.9	9.7 ± 1.1	30.6 ± 1.7

The means \pm standard deviations with the same letters in the same columns are not significantly different ($p < 0.05$, Tukey test).

TTA: Total Titratable Acidity; TSS: Total Soluble Solids; DMC: Dry Matter Content

3.3.2 Panel performance

Panel performance was evaluated as described by Bugaud et al. (2022). The results obtained are summarized below as follows:

- One panelist out of 10 had a repeatability lesser than 50% for the attribute firmness;
- One panelist out of 10 had a disagreement greater than 50% for the attribute sweetness and for the overall quality;
- The attribute color was not discriminant

Figure 5. Radar displaying the average values obtained by the panel for each product and attribute on a 0 to 10 scale

3.3.3 Sensory attributes of boiled plantain

Ranking the sensory attributes of boiled plantain samples on a scale of 0 to 10 showed that sweetness, humidity, and color scored below 5 across the different genotypes. Firmness was significantly higher (≥ 6.0) for *Batard*, Kelong Mekintu, and PITA 23, while PITA 21 had the lowest firmness. Conversely, humidity scores were highest among landraces, with Kelong Mekintu achieving the best rating for color. Landraces scored the lowest for sweetness, with *CARBAP 969* having the highest mean score at 3.6. Overall acceptability was significantly higher (≈ 8) for the landraces (*Batard*, *Kelong Mekintu*, and *Big Ebanga*), with *CARBAP 969* being the only bred hybrid that was statistically comparable to them. PITA 21 was the least accepted (Table 7).

A PCA analysis of sensory attributes and overall acceptability explained 86.5% of the variance, predominantly on the first axis (67.2%). This axis was positively associated with overall acceptability, firmness, and color, linked to the most favored landrace samples (*Batard*, *Big Ebanga*, and Kelong Mekintu), while humidity negatively impacted the least liked sample (PITA 21). Sweetness was solely represented on the second axis, relating specifically to the *CARBAP 969* sample.

Table 6. Mean attribute scores for boiled plantain samples during Quantitative Descriptive Analysis

Accessions	Firmness	Humidity	Sweetness	Colour	Overall quality
CARBAP 969	5.4 ^{bc}	5.4 ^{ab}	4.0 ^a	4.3 ^{bc}	7.8 ^{ab}
CARBAP K74	4.7 ^{cd}	5.4 ^{ab}	1.8 ^c	4.8 ^b	6.6 ^c
PITA 14	5.3 ^{bc}	5.3 ^{abc}	2.3 ^{bc}	4.9 ^b	7.1 ^{abc}
PITA 21	3.6 ^d	6.0 ^a	1.8 ^c	3.3 ^c	5.3 ^d
PITA 23	6.0 ^{ab}	4.6 ^{bcd}	2.2 ^{bc}	4.7 ^{bc}	7.0 ^{bc}
PITA 27	5.6 ^{abc}	4.8 ^{bcd}	2.3 ^{bc}	4.5 ^{bc}	7.1 ^{bc}
Batard	6.7 ^a	3.6 ^d	1.8 ^c	5.0 ^{ab}	7.9 ^{ab}
Big Ebanga	5.6 ^{abc}	4.2 ^{cd}	1.8 ^c	5.2 ^{ab}	7.8 ^{ab}
Kelong mekintu	6.5 ^{ab}	4.4 ^{bcd}	2.8 ^b	6.3 ^a	8.2 ^a
AVERAGE	5.5	4.9	2.3	4.8	7.2

The means with the same letters in the same columns are not significantly different ($p < 0.05$, Tukey test).

Figure 6. Mapping of the sensory attributes and the overall acceptability of the boiled plantain samples during QDA

3.3.4 Instrumental texture analysis of boiled plantain

The texture attributes of boiled plantain for each test type are summarized in Table 8. Significant differences were found among the various clones. Texture Profile Analysis (TPA) indicated that *Batard* had the highest values for hardness, gumminess, and chewiness. *CARBAP K74* showed the greatest springiness and adhesiveness, while PITA 21 was the most resilient and *Big Ebanga* was the most cohesive. Penetrometry measurements revealed that *Big Ebanga* was the hardest clone, and PITA 21 achieved the highest distance at Fmax, with *CARBAP K74* exhibiting the largest area under the curve.

Table 7. Mean texture attributes of boiled plantain samples

Accessions	TPA parameters							Penetrometry parameters		
	Hardness (g)	Resilience (%)	Springiness (%)	Adhesiveness (g.s)	Cohesiveness	Gumminess	Chewiness	Hardness (g)	Distance at Fmax (mm)	Area under the curve (g.s)
<i>CARBAP 969</i>	6794.3±1848.1 ^{cd}	95.1±17.4 ^{cd}	90.2±11.6 ^b	229.5±128.9 ^{ab}	0.2±0.1 ^b	1061.4±346.2 ^{bc}	941.5±273.5 ^{cd}	NA	NA	NA
<i>CARBAP K74</i>	7635.4±1818.4 ^c	109.0±24.8 ^c	102.0±21.5 ^a	-132.5±133.6 ^a	0.2±0.0 ^b	1226.7±368.9 ^b	1235.8±392.8 ^{bc}	422.3±50.4 ^a	4.3±0.9 ^c	4598.4±519.7 ^a
<i>PITA 14</i>	3356.0±452.5 ^f	151.1±22.5 ^b	86.4±8.6 ^b	393.6±234.0 ^{bc}	0.1±0.0 ^c	320.4±68.3 ^d	264.2±62.8 ^e	58.5±15.4 ^{de}	6.6±1.9 ^{ab}	384.7±112.5 ^{ef}
<i>PITA 21</i>	2929.3±737.7 ^f	212.4±52.8 ^a	89.7±11.2 ^b	376.9±249.9 ^{abc}	0.1±0.0 ^c	300.1±98.8 ^d	244.0±67.7 ^e	49.4±13.4 ^e	7.7±1.8 ^a	281.4±73.2 ^f
<i>PITA 23</i>	5992.8±590.4 ^{de}	112.8±19.8 ^c	62.2±9.8 ^d	1051.4±544.9 ^d	0.1±0.0 ^c	543.4±179.5 ^{cd}	337.6±138.5 ^e	84.0±29.1 ^{cd}	5.5±0.8 ^{bc}	560.7±174.8 ^{de}
<i>PITA 27</i>	5567.9±1852.5 ^e	108.0±31.1 ^c	82.5±12.6 ^{bc}	188.4±132.4 ^{ab}	0.1±0.0 ^{bc}	725.0±179.9 ^{bcd}	577.8±170.5 ^{de}	63.0±9.7 ^{de}	5.6±1.2 ^{bc}	420.6±81.1 ^{ef}
<i>Batard</i>	11000.3±1428.0 ^a	72.6±11.6 ^d	71.6±8.7 ^{cd}	-170.0±85.2 ^{ab}	0.2±0.1 ^a	2450.5±840.8 ^a	1703.4±441.4 ^a	199.8±81.7 ^b	7.1±0.8 ^{ab}	1342.7±391.8 ^c
<i>Big Ebanga</i>	9068.5±1884.6 ^b	74.8±21.2 ^d	75.2±13.7 ^c	171.1±107.0 ^{ab}	0.2±0.1 ^a	2098.4±918.7 ^a	1499.3±494.7 ^{ab}	423.8±93.1 ^a	4.1±0.2 ^c	2728.9±1303.5 ^b
<i>Kelong</i>										
<i>Mekintu</i>	7362.4±535.0 ^c	103.4±17.0 ^c	71.0±10.9 ^{cd}	-566.1±424.4 ^c	0.1±0.0 ^{bc}	802.4±171.4 ^{bcd}	539.6±136.9 ^e	102.8±16.2 ^c	6.9±1.0 ^{ab}	687.5±98.4 ^d
AVERAGE	6634.1±1238.6	115.5±24.2	73.4±12.1	-364.3±226.7	0.1±0.0	1058.1±352.5	816.6±242.1	578.2±34.3	5.3±1.0	1222.7±306.1

NA: Not available

3.4 Correlation between instrumental texture analysis and sensory analysis

PCA plots combining instrumental and sensory texture analysis explained 83% of the variance in the attributes, with 61.1% and 21.8% attributed to the first and second components, respectively (Figure 7). The bred hybrids PITA 14, PITA 27, and PITA 21 were closely related and associated with resilience and sensory humidity, which affects the mouthfeel of boiled plantain. *CARBAP K74*, a plantain-like hybrid, was characterized by a springy, hard, and adhesive texture and was distinctly clustered apart from other genotypes based on penetration attributes, making it less preferred by consumers.

Big Ebanga and *Batard*, both landraces, were differentiated by penetrometry but not by TPA. They were associated with a cohesive, chewy, gummy, hard, and firm texture but lacked humidity, making them more favorable among consumers compared to bred hybrids. PITA 23 and the landrace Kelong Mekintu had similar textures but were not linked in terms of sensory humidity or firmness, suggesting an intermediate preference among consumers.

The only significant correlation between penetration and TPA attributes was between penetration hardness and TPA chewiness ($r^2 = 0.63$, $P = 0.048$). Several significant correlations were also found between TPA and sensory texture, as outlined below:

- TPA hardness and sensory humidity ($r = -0.87$)
- TPA resilience and sensory firmness ($r = -0.74$)
- TPA resilience and sensory humidity ($r = 0.92$)
- TPA springiness and sensory firmness ($r = -0.77$)
- TPA gumminess and sensory humidity ($r = -0.76$)

There were no significant correlations between penetration and the sensory texture of boiled plantain.

Figure 7. PCA plots of instrumental and sensory texture of boiled plantain genotypes

3.5 Estimation of physicochemical and texture attributes using QDA data

The determination of some thresholds of boiled plantain quality traits was carried out using data obtained from consumer testing (JAR), QDA, Texture and biophysical analyses (dry matter content (DMC), Total soluble solids (TSS), Total titratable acidity (TTA) and colour). Pearson correlation coefficients were obtained from these data at 5% threshold (Table 9.), and plots (Figure 8) were drawn to determine R² values between JAR data and QDA data.

Only the plots of firmness and colour (JAR vs QDA) were found to show a linear relationship for which R² was greater than 0.5, making them candidates for determining thresholds for certain biophysical values. While wetness (JAR vs QDA) presented an R² value of 0.29, that of sweetness on the other hand was very low (0.0015). This could be due to two reasons: (i) the sample size was relatively low, since with 4 samples may not have contrasted between them, and (ii) the characteristic “sweet” is not perceived the same way by the consumers, that is why there was a discrepancy in values observed for this characteristic on QDA and JAR.

Based on the maximum JAR data obtained (65%), the optimal value could be set to 70%, while the acceptable value has been set to 50% (y=50%). Based on this, and taking into consideration the graphs of firmness and color, the corresponding acceptable values for QDA are:

- QDA firmness

From the equation: $y = 15.826x - 39.642$

$x = \text{QDA firmness} = 5.66$

- QDA color

From the equation: $y = 43.648x - 168.53$

$x = \text{QDA colour} = 5.01$

i) Threshold values using QDA firmness

DMC, TPA hardness and TPA resilience were the traits that presented R^2 values greater than 0.5 with QDA firmness (Figure 9.). Using the various equations in Figure 8 for the corresponding traits, with $x = \text{QDA firmness} = 5.66$, the following values are obtained:

DMC = 32.03%

TPA hardness = 8737.31g

TPA resilience = 291.56

ii) Threshold values using QDA colour

Using QDA colour, TSS and DMC were the traits whose R^2 were greater than 0.5 (Figure 10.). Using the various equations in Figure 10 for the corresponding traits, with $x = \text{QDA colour} = 5.01$, the following values are obtained:

DMC = 32.54%

TSS = 13.9°Brix

Based on the above calculations, the threshold values of some boiled plantain traits are: $\text{DMC} > 32.03\%$; $\text{TPA hardness} > 8737.31\text{g}$; $\text{TPA resilience} > 291.56$; $\text{TSS} > 13.9^\circ\text{Brix}$. These values are obtained mathematically and can be improved with a larger sample size and the combination of some variables

Table 8. Pearson correlation coefficients between the various variables

Variables	JAR colour	JAR Firmness	JAR Wetness	JAR Sweetness	QDA Firmness	QDA Wetness	QDA Sweetness	QDA Colour	TTA	TSS	L*	a*	b*	DMC	Hardn	Resil.	Spring.	Adhesi.	Cohesi.	Gummi.	Chew.	Delta E	
JAR colour	1,00																						
JAR Firmness	0,93	1,00																					
JAR Wetness	0,67	0,78	1,00																				
JAR Sweetness	0,87	0,95	0,94	1,00																			
QDA Firmness	0,86	0,98	0,74	0,91	1,00																		
QDA Wetness	-0,97	-0,93	-0,55	-0,80	-0,88	1,00																	
QDA Sweetness	-0,45	-0,21	0,36	0,04	-0,16	0,56	1,00																
QDA Colour	0,71	0,44	0,01	0,28	0,33	-0,73	-0,91	1,00															
TTA	0,36	0,59	0,19	0,39	0,73	-0,52	-0,16	0,02	1,00														
TSS	0,73	0,70	0,10	0,44	0,72	-0,86	-0,76	0,72	0,71	1,00													
L*	-0,46	-0,69	-0,94	-0,84	-0,70	0,37	-0,56	0,29	-0,36	-0,01	1,00												
a*	0,51	0,23	0,34	0,34	0,04	-0,35	-0,29	0,63	-0,61	-0,01	-0,01	1,00											
b*	0,03	-0,03	0,53	0,27	-0,16	0,19	0,54	-0,19	-0,71	-0,65	-0,40	0,64	1,00										
DMC	0,98	0,91	0,52	0,78	0,85	-1,00	-0,60	0,78	0,47	0,86	-0,32	0,40	-0,18	1,00									
Hardness	0,89	0,86	0,36	0,66	0,85	-0,97	-0,66	0,73	0,65	0,96	-0,22	0,17	-0,43	0,96	1,00								
Resilience	-0,98	-0,94	-0,80	-0,94	-0,86	0,92	0,28	-0,59	-0,31	-0,60	0,60	-0,54	-0,19	-0,92	-0,80	1,00							
Springiness	-0,98	-0,96	-0,81	-0,95	-0,89	0,93	0,26	-0,56	-0,36	-0,61	0,63	-0,49	-0,16	-0,92	-0,81	1,00	1,00						
Adhesiveness	0,01	-0,21	-0,74	-0,47	-0,22	-0,15	-0,89	0,64	0,05	0,52	0,85	0,02	-0,67	0,19	0,32	0,18	0,20	1,00					
Cohesiveness	0,98	0,85	0,64	0,82	0,73	-0,92	-0,47	0,77	0,16	0,63	-0,38	0,68	0,18	0,93	0,80	-0,96	-0,95	0,03	1,00				
Gumminess	0,96	0,88	0,47	0,74	0,83	-0,99	-0,64	0,81	0,47	0,88	-0,27	0,40	-0,21	1,00	0,97	-0,90	-0,89	0,25	0,92	1,00			
Chewiness	0,86	0,74	0,21	0,53	0,70	-0,93	-0,81	0,88	0,49	0,95	-0,02	0,31	-0,42	0,94	0,97	-0,74	-0,74	0,50	0,81	0,96	1,00		
Delta E	0,28	0,52	0,89	0,72	0,54	-0,18	0,72	-0,45	0,23	-0,19	-0,98	-0,03	0,50	0,13	0,02	-0,45	-0,47	-0,94	0,21	0,07	-0,19	1,00	

Values in bold are different from 0 with a significance level $\alpha=0,05$

Figure 8. Plots of %JAR vs QDA Firmness (A), QDA Wetness (B), QDA Sweetness (C) and QDA Colour (D)

Figure 9. Plots of DMC (A), Hardness (B) and Resilience (C) vs QDA firmness

Figure 10. Plots of TSS (A) and DMC (B) vs QDA colour

4 CONCLUSION

This report investigated priority quality traits thresholds through correlation between instrumental and sensory texture attributes of boiled plantain genotypes in Cameroon. Landraces were rated as just-about-right for over 45% of the sensory attributes firmness, color, wetness and sweetness. Among the bred hybrids, *CARBAP 969* was the top performer, followed by *PITA 14*, both showing overall quality comparable to landraces. This finding suggests the potential for developing improved bred hybrids that combine resilience, high productivity, and consumer-preferred traits.

Of the four QDA attributes, three were informative: firmness and color showed a positive relationship with overall liking, while humidity had a negative correlation. Color and firmness emerged as the most significant sensory characteristics, receiving higher scores from panelists for landraces. Significant correlations were found between TPA and sensory texture, with negative correlations for sensory humidity and hardness, as well as sensory firmness and resilience, while resilience and sensory humidity were positively correlated. Threshold values for some priority quality traits are: DMC>32.03%; TPA hardness>8737.31g; TPA resilience>291.56; TSS>13.9°Brix. Regarding color, no threshold value was found with the available data.

Though penetrometry was more effective in discriminating genotypes than TPA, it did not correlate well with sensory texture. To address this issue, a larger population of plantain genotypes, including bred

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